

INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS LEGAL POLITICS IN INDONESIA IN ORDER TO OPTIMIZE COMMERCIALIZATION EFFORTS AND THEIR ECONOMIC BENEFITS FOR INDONESIA

Yudistira Rusydi¹, Serlika Aprita², Dwi Putri³

^{1,2}Faculty of Law, Universitas Muhammadiyah Bengkulu
Corresponding Author: 5312lika@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study examines how Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) policies in Indonesia operate and whether they have been able to encourage the commercialization of intellectual works. Although Indonesia has adjusted its laws to international standards such as TRIPs, practice in the field shows that IPR is still more focused on protection than economic utilization. Low literacy among the public and business actors, weak law enforcement, and less than optimal support from the government and industry are the main factors that hinder commercialization. In fact, IPR has great potential to encourage the growth of the creative economy, increase exports, and attract investment. The results of the study indicate that Indonesia needs a more progressive IPR legal policy model, which not only secures the rights of creators but also opens up space for utilization, downstreaming, and commercial cooperation. By strengthening regulations, the innovation ecosystem, and public understanding, IPR can become one of the driving forces of the national economy.

Keywords: *Economic Growth, Intellectual Property Rights, Law Enforcement, Legal Politics.*